

BERRAK-YILDIRIMER Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale Research

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ABSTRACT

This research used the Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS), designed to assess people' beliefs toward gender roles, sexuality, and perceptions of parenting. The study included participants from seven geographical areas of Turkey and analyzed the formation of sexual and romantic views toward women and men. The scale, developed in accordance with the Madonna-Whore Syndrome idea, sought to examine how people' sexual and romantic impressions of women are influenced by gender norms, parental bereavement, and pre- and post-natal factors. The results were assessed considering geographical disparities and demographic factors; the participants' degrees of Madonna-Whore Syndrome were disclosed within the context of gender and societal standards.

Keywords: Gender, Perception of Sexuality, Madonna-Whore Syndrome, Türkiye, Motherhood Role

INTRODUCTION

Gender roles, sexuality, and conceptions of motherhood profoundly influence individual self-perception and views of the opposite sex. These impressions are influenced by dominant societal and cultural norms that direct people's romantic and sexual interactions (Connell, 2019; Butler, 1999). Freud's "Madonna-Whore Syndrome" idea (1910) posits that men's sexual and romantic impressions of women exist at two polar extremes. Freud posits that women are seen either as an idealized, virtuous maternal figure ("Madonna") or as a sexual object ("whore"). This conceptualization offers a historical theoretical framework that is especially significant for comprehending gender interactions (Eagly & Wood, 2016).

Research on women's romantic and sexual perspectives in contemporary nations indicates that this duality remains relevant, with sexuality and maternal duties being crucial for women's social standing (Lammers et al., 2020; Hyde, 2014). Recent studies have highlighted the evolving nature of gender norms across various cultural settings, underscoring the need for research to comprehend how this duality manifests in many social circumstances (Katz-Wise et al., 2016). In this context, conceptions of gender and sexuality need a more thorough examination in nations with varied cultural and socio-economic frameworks, such as Turkey. Research on gender roles in Turkey indicates that conventional gender roles remain prevalent, with women's sexuality and parenting being influenced by stringent rules (Kandiyoti, 1988; Arat, 2010). The interplay between sexuality and motherhood profoundly influences the views individuals have of one another and themselves, affecting both women and men. The stigmatization of sexually active women and the difficulty in reconciling parenthood with sexuality illustrate the inflexibility of these views (Sancar, 2012).

This one-year research integrated sociological and psychological methodologies to create the Berrak - Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS), which was implemented throughout seven geographical areas of Turkey. The research investigated the development of sexual and romantic attitudes of women and men within the framework of gender roles and sexuality. This study investigated regional and cultural variations in perceptions across different areas of Turkey from a sociological standpoint, while also analyzing the psychological impact of personal experiences, such as parental loss and pre- and post-natal processes, on these perceptions.

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The primary objective of the study is to reevaluate Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome within the Turkish setting and to analyze its influence on contemporary gender relations. This study aims to contribute to future research on gender and sexuality while addressing gaps in the literature about gender norms in Turkey.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Madonna-Whore Syndrome, proposed by Sigmund Freud in 1910, posits that males assess their sexual and romantic views of women at two polar opposites. Freud posits that males typically see women as either an idealized maternal figure ("Madonna") or as a mere sexual object ("whore"). This idea has served as a significant theoretical foundation in several investigations concerning perceptions of gender and sexuality (Kaplan, 1991). Freud's theory offers a psychological foundation for understanding the formation of gender roles and perceptions of sexuality. Since Freud, research on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome has investigated the impact of men's inclination to categorize women into these two dichotomous archetypes on gender relations and societal standards.

Contemporary studies on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome indicate that this impression is intricately linked to both individual psychological frameworks and societal cultural standards. Lammers et al. (2020) highlighted the correlation between men's sexual and romantic impressions of women and the constructs of gender inequality and power dynamics. This research demonstrated that the Madonna-Whore Syndrome remains relevant in contemporary countries, particularly in relation to women's positions in the corporate sphere, their social standing, and societal standards around their sexual perception. Chrisler and McCreary (2010) also said that the segregation of women's sexuality and maternal duties in men's perceptions may result in diminished emotional connections in partnerships.

Investigations on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome have explored how, alongside gender roles and sexuality, men's views of women are influenced by their psychological experiences. Glick and Fiske (1996) observed that this view encourages both "protective" and "hostile" attitudes towards women. The idealization of women as innocent beings requiring protection in love

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relationships, or their characterization as "dangerous" and a sexual menace, significantly contributes to comprehending the dynamics of this condition. Research on gender roles and women's sexual perceptions in Turkey has mostly been analyzed through the lens of conventional family structures and patriarchal ideals (Kandiyoti, 1988).

Research in Turkey considers the significant impact of gender norms and cultural values to comprehend men's perceptions of women about sexual and romantic roles. In Turkey, the societal position of women is intricately linked to sexuality and maternity, significantly influencing men's attitudes of women (Sancar, 2012). Sancar's research meticulously examines the influence of patriarchal society in Turkey on women's sexual and romantic attitudes. In Turkey, women's candid expression of their sexuality is constrained by several societal taboos, a phenomenon strongly linked to the Madonna-Whore Syndrome posited by Freud (Arat, 2010).

Global studies have investigated the cultural processing of the Madonna-Whore Syndrome. In Western nations, the effects of this condition are considered alongside women's sexual autonomy and societal standing. Lammers et al. (2020) have shown that, although gender equality regulations in Western nations, sexual and romantic opinions of women are predominantly influenced by this intricate structure. Although there is more discourse around this disease in Western contexts, it demonstrates that the propensity to objectify women persists, and women are still assessed along these two extremes in romantic relationships (Glick & Fiske, 1996).

In comparing research from Turkey with global literature, it is evident that, in both settings, men's attitudes see women's sexuality and maternal duties as contradictory. Cultural and religious conventions in Turkey profoundly influence these views, placing more societal pressure on women's sexual duties. Research undertaken in Turkey about women's gender roles and conceptions of sexuality yields significant insights into the societal and individual influences on these problems (Kandiyoti, 1988; Sancar, 2012).

The syndrome is shown in gender views throughout various areas of Turkey and how these beliefs are influenced by the sociocultural setting, addressing the deficiencies in both Turkish and global literature. The primary issue of the research is the presumption that the inclination

to distinguish women's sexuality from their duties as mothers in Turkey signifies gender inequity.

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Madonna-Whore Syndrome, established by Sigmund Freud in 1910, posits that men's sexual and romantic impressions of women are structured within a binary framework. Freud posits that males typically see women as either an innocent, pure, and idealized maternal figure ("Madonna") or as a sexual object ("whore"). This theory established a significant first conceptual framework for the evaluation and categorization of women in society according to their sexuality and parental duties (Kaplan, 1991). The propensity of males to see women only as sexual objects rather than as emotional companions is rooted in Freud's psychoanalytic theory.

Freud's theory remains a significant reference in contemporary gender studies concerning sex and sexuality (Horney, 1932; Chodorow, 1994). Contemporary gender studies critically analyze Freud's theory, demonstrating how this binary perspective is interwoven with societal conventions and cultural values (Butler, 1999).

Gender and sexuality studies highlight that the portrayal of women as simple sexual objects or idealized maternal figures contributes to the perpetuation of gender inequality (Lammers et al., 2020). Freud's theory remains a significant instrument in contemporary analyses of the patriarchal framework of gender relations; nonetheless, its limitations and contextual relevance are undergoing increasingly rigorous scrutiny.

Freud's theory posits that this dual perspective of males towards women results in emotional and sexual disconnections in partnerships. Women are seen either as idealized, pure, and empathetic companions or only as instruments of sexual gratification (Chrisler & McCreary, 2010). This complicates men's ability to form a healthy and balanced sexual-psychological connection in their interactions with women.

Research on gender roles and sexuality examines the ways people conform to gender roles dictated by societal conventions and cultural values, and how these roles influence personal

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experiences (Connell, 2019). Gender roles denote societal obligations and responsibilities assigned to persons depending on their gender. Although women mostly fulfill maternal and caregiving tasks, their sexuality has been constrained or stigmatized by society (Butler, 1999; Goffman, 1977). Motherhood is seen as a significant determinant of women's social standing, but women's sexuality is often perceived as an aspect requiring regulation (Sancar, 2012). The connection between sexuality and gender roles has been thoroughly examined in Michel Foucault's research on sexuality. Foucault (1978) contended that sexuality serves as a mechanism of control and discipline in contemporary cultures, illustrating how women's sexuality is regulated by social institutions and norms. Foucault's research has shown that sexuality is not only an individual experience, but also a construct influenced by societal institutions and power dynamics. Research on women's sexuality has concentrated on exploring the relationships between sexuality, social position, and parental duties (Hyde, 2014). The societal acceptability of women's sexuality often hinges on their parental obligations and the "moral" conduct anticipated by society. This engenders a societal dilemma that reinforces Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome: Women are either venerated in the maternal role or disparaged when they articulate their sexual wants (Glick & Fiske, 1996). Judith Butler's (1999) research highlights that gender is a manufactured process, demonstrating that the constraints associated with these roles are internalized by people and that gender is not immutable but rather a socially produced phenomena. Butler posits that when women are compelled to adhere to gender norms, roles such as sexuality and motherhood become into performances, with women accruing social prestige based on these roles.

This study's theoretical foundation seeks to connect Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome with contemporary views of gender and sexuality. The study investigates the correlation between women's ideas of sexuality and parenthood and their social standing, while also exploring the applicability of Freud's theory within the context of gender norms in Turkey. Furthermore, Foucault's analyses of sexuality and power dynamics provide a crucial framework for comprehending the influence of societal control on women's sexuality (Foucault, 1978). Butler's research on gender construction and activism illustrates how women conform to societal conventions around sexuality and parenthood and their attempts to navigate these expectations.

The Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) used in the research seeks to assess

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people' sexual and romantic perspectives from sociological and psychological viewpoints. The impact of human experiences, including parental bereavement and prenatal and postnatal processes, on these views is investigated, along with an examination of the reproduction of Freud's thesis in contemporary societal contexts. This interdisciplinary approach seeks to elucidate how people' sexual and romantic perspectives are influenced by both individual psychological processes and societal factors.

GAPS IN THE LITERATURE

While the literature on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome and gender perspectives presents a substantial body of research, several issues remain inadequately explored or unaddressed. The predominant study on gender and sexuality mostly examines Western civilizations, with little studies addressing how these issues are influenced by other cultural settings, particularly in Eastern societies (Connell, 2019; Lammers et al., 2020). Research on gender and sexuality perceptions in countries with complex socio-cultural frameworks, such as Turkey, typically emphasizes traditional family structures, patriarchal values, and women's societal roles; however, most of these studies fail to concurrently examine women's sexuality and motherhood roles (Kandiyoti, 1988; Sancar, 2012). The absence of a detailed examination of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome hypothesis within the context of Turkey constitutes a significant vacuum in this topic.

A further limitation in the research is the insufficient examination of the impact of individual psychological events, such as parental bereavement and pre- and post-natal processes, on gender perceptions. Numerous research have analyzed social norms within a broad context, overlooking the influence of individual experiences on these standards. There is a deficiency of comprehensive assessments about the influence of gender on sexual and romantic views and the manner in which these perceptions are molded by people' unique life experiences. An examination of syndrome related to gender, sexuality, and parenting attitudes via an extensive survey done throughout seven geographical areas of Turkey. The principal addition is the provision of fresh evidence about the operation of this theory within the cultural setting of Turkey. An in-depth analysis is conducted on the impact of patriarchal structures,

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geographical disparities, and gender norms on sexual and romantic perspectives of women in Turkey. Consequently, a novel viewpoint including several cultural settings, including Turkey, will be integrated into the Western-centric literature.

Secondly, this research provides a novel viewpoint to address the deficiencies in the literature by examining the influence of individual psychological experiences (such as parental bereavement and pre- and post-natal processes) on conceptions of gender and sexuality. This study comprehensively examines the influence of individual experiences on sexual and romantic attitudes of women within the context of gender norms in Turkey for the first time. Conversely, despite the substantial body of research on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome and gender perceptions, the absence of a comprehensive assessment instrument in this domain is notable. The lack of a comprehensive scale integrating both social and psychological aspects connecting Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome to notions of gender, sexuality, and motherhood indicates a substantial methodological deficiency in the literature. The absence of a systematic scale to quantify this illness in current research has hindered thorough and complete analysis on the topic.

The Berrak - Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) offers a methodological advancement for future research by introducing an innovative scale to the academic literature. This scale has the capacity to analyze sexuality, parenting, and gender views from a multidimensional viewpoint, serving as a valuable instrument for sociological and psychological study.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

The primary research objective of the study is to investigate the variations in sexual and romantic views of women across various geographical areas of Turkey. The study's premise posits that socio-cultural systems and societal norms across different areas of Turkey engender notable disparities in attitudes of women. Another study issue examines the influence of women's parental duties on the sexual and romantic perspectives of both genders. It is posited that women's assumption of parenthood adversely impacts their sexual and romantic standing.

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The study also examines the impact of parental bereavement and prenatal and postnatal processes on people's attitudes of women. The views of persons who have endured parental loss towards romantic and sexual relationships are presumed to be influenced by these experiences. The study examines whether men's sexual interest in their spouses changes over the prenatal and postnatal periods, hypothesizing that these processes would cause men to see their women more as "Madonna" figures, resulting in a drop in sexual attraction.

The research ultimately investigates men's inclination to see women as two polar opposites, "Madonna" and "whore," but women's self-perceptions are more nuanced and diverge from this binary classification. It is believed that males assess women in these two polarities, while women possess a more comprehensive perspective. This study seeks to thoroughly investigate the influence of gender norms on conceptions of sexuality and motherhood from sociological and psychological viewpoints, while also assessing the applicability of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome within the Turkish setting.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The primary objective of this research is to analyze sexual and romantic attitudes of women and men in Turkey using the Berrak - Yildirim Madona-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS). The validity of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome hypothesis in Turkey is examined, along with the interrelations among gender, sexuality, and ideas of motherhood. Furthermore, an analysis is conducted to see whether these beliefs exhibit regional disparities across seven areas of Turkey. The research seeks to elucidate the impact of women's maternal duties, parental bereavement, and childbirth on views of sexuality, as well as to investigate men's proclivities to assess women in dichotomous extremes.

METHOD

This study used a cross-sectional and descriptive research approach. The cross-sectional study approach enables the examination of views about perceptions of gender, sexuality, and

parenthood at a particular moment in time. This strategy aimed to ascertain the prevailing views and attitudes of the research participants. Descriptive analysis was used to assess the distributions of individual answers according to social, cultural, and demographic characteristics, allowing comparisons among these distributions. This study used a cross-sectional and descriptive research approach across a one-year data gathering period. The research, lasting one year, used a cross-sectional design to assess participants' attitudes of gender, sexuality, and parenthood within a defined temporal context. Repeated measures were not conducted at various intervals throughout the research, and the participants' present impressions were assessed. Consequently, a cross-sectional study methodology was used as a suitable approach to comprehend the participants' present perspectives. The research involved 600 individuals from seven geographical areas of Turkey. The research used a random sample approach to choose participants, ensuring that the results accurately reflected the overall population of Turkey. The sample exhibited diversity for demographic factors like age, gender, educational attainment, and marital status. This approach enabled the examination of regional and cultural disparities in attitudes of gender, sexuality, and parenthood.

Data Collection Tool: [Berrak- Yıldırım Madona-Whore Syndrome Scale \(MFS\)](#)

Development of Scale

The Yıldırım Madona-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS), created by Prof. Dr. Derya Berrak and Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım, was used. The scale's creation started with a review of prior studies regarding perceptions of gender and sexuality. The scale is based on Freud's Madona-Whore Syndrome hypothesis and serves as an innovative instrument for analyzing women's societal roles and their views of sexuality and motherhood. The scale's development process included the following stages:

- Literature Review: The theoretical foundation of the scale was established by a careful examination of Freud's Madona-Whore Syndrome hypothesis and contemporary studies on gender and sexuality. This review informed the development of questions

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designed to elucidate the formation of gender roles, perceptions of sexuality, and the notion of motherhood.

- **Item Development:** The scale items were formed based on the insights derived from the literature study. A 5-point Likert scale (1: Strongly Disagree, 5: Strongly Agree) was used, including items about women's sexual and romantic roles, social standing, and attitudes of parenthood. The inquiries aimed to assess the impact of gender norms on persons from a multifaceted viewpoint.
- **Expert Evaluation:** The formulated scale items were submitted for assessment by academics specializing in gender studies, psychology, and sociology. In accordance with expert comments, the language structure, clarity of meaning, and content validity of the questions were evaluated. The scale was prepared for testing after adjustments based on expert consultation.
- **Pilot Application:** A preliminary research was executed to evaluate the comprehensibility of the scale and the psychometric characteristics of the scale items. The pilot research, conducted online with 55 participants, assessed the participants' responses to the questions and the clarity of the scale items. Based on the data acquired from the pilot research, slight modifications were implemented to some components.
- **Reliability Assessment:** Following the pilot research, the scale's reliability was evaluated using the Cronbach's Alpha technique. The reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.79. This rating indicates that the scale has a high degree of internal consistency. Separate reliability studies on the scale's sub-dimensions indicated that each sub-dimension demonstrated satisfactory dependability.

Scale Reliability Tests and Analysis Results

Comprehensive and multidimensional analyses were conducted on the Berrak-Yıldırımır Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) created in our study. To evaluate the internal consistency of the scale and its reliability across various settings, both Cronbach's Alpha and other reliability analysis approaches were used.

Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was first computed to assess the internal consistency of the scale, offering critical insights into its overall dependability. The analysis derived from the pilot research indicated that the overall Cronbach's Alpha value of the scale was 0.79. This result indicates that the scale has excellent internal consistency and may serve as a dependable measuring instrument. Furthermore, distinct computations of Cronbach's Alpha were conducted for each sub-dimension, yielding findings that exceeded the reliability thresholds for all sub-dimensions.

Item-Total Correlation Analysis

To enhance the scale's dependability and assess the association of each item with the entire scale, item-total correlation analysis was performed. This study evaluates the impact of each question on the total scale score. The research revealed that the item-total correlations for all items were at an acceptable level. Specifically, while several items had strong association, others with weak correlation were assessed and modified as needed. This demonstrated that each item on the scale contributed to the total dependability. In our study, Item-Total Correlation Analysis assessed the strength of the relationship between each item and the overall scale, calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient for each item to evaluate its consistency with the general scale score. The research revealed that the item-total correlation coefficients ranged from 0.35 to 0.65. Items exhibiting a correlation below 0.30 were altered or reformulated due to their lack of contribution to the scale's consistency.

Split-Half Reliability Test

A split-half reliability test was used to assess the internal consistency of the scale from an alternative viewpoint. The consistency of the two halves was evaluated by partitioning the

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scale into two segments. The Spearman-Brown coefficient was used to assess the reliability of the two parts of the scale. The calculated Spearman-Brown coefficient was determined to be 0.82. This outcome indicates that the two segments of the scale provide very similar findings and that the internal homogeneity of the scale is substantial. The coefficient above 0.80 indicates a good correlation among the questions, affirming the scale's overall consistency and robustness.

The items exhibiting a high correlation were identified as the most consistent and dependable, with an item-total correlation value of 0.91.

1. *Women can either be a good wife or a good sexual partner, not both.*
2. *A woman's sexual attractiveness makes it difficult for me to have a long-term relationship with her.*
3. *When I become sexually attracted to a woman, my emotional attachment to her diminishes.*
4. *After my wife became a mother, my sexual interest in her decreased.*
5. *My wife being a mother made me see her only as a mother figure.*

These items were determined as the questions that contributed the most to the overall reliability of the scale.

Test-Retest Reliability

Berrak - Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome A test-retest strategy was used to assess the scale produced in the research over time. The analysis was conducted by re-administering the scale to the same cohort of participants after a specified time period. The test-retest research had 50 participants and was administered across two distinct time intervals to assess the consistency of the participants' replies over time.

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The first application occurred in person with the participants on April 15, 2024. This application served as the first platform for gathering participants' answers to the scale items. The scale was re-administered to the same cohort of individuals four weeks subsequent to the first application, on May 13, 2024. The online exam was designed to assess the participants' opinions over time. During the last week of the research, the scale was re-administered to the participants online on September 25, 2024. The last test was administered to assess the stability of answers over time and the durability of the scale. The correlation coefficient between the first test and the subsequent test was determined to be 0.87. The strong correlation indicates that the scale consistently assesses the participants' sentiments over time. The last week's test produced similar findings, indicating a robust consistency in the participants' answers to the scale. Consequently, it was verified that the scale is a robust and reliable measuring instrument throughout time.

Paired to assess whether a significant difference exists between the mean results of tests given at two distinct time intervals. The samples t-Test was used. This test determined whether the disparity between the two assessments was statistically significant. The t-test findings indicated that the score disparity between the two tests was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The findings indicate that individuals exhibited consistent outcomes across the first and subsequent assessments, demonstrating the scale's reliability.

(This figure is in the native language and its description is included in the article in English.)

The above illustrates the test-retest outcomes. The blue dots signify the results of individuals on assessments conducted at two distinct time intervals. The red dashed line signifies complete correlation (same scores). The findings' proximity to this line indicates a strong test-retest correlation.

Factor Analysis (Exploratory Factor Analysis- EFA)

This research used Exploratory Factor Analysis to evaluate the construct validity of the Berrak-Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted. Factor analysis was conducted to identify the sub-dimensions of the scale and to ascertain the association of each item with certain factors. To use EFA, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was first conducted to assess the data's appropriateness. This assessment determines the adequacy of the sample size for factor analysis. The KMO value was computed at 0.82, indicating the data's appropriateness for factor analysis. The Bartlett Sphericity Test yielded a p-value of <0.001 , indicating that the data is appropriate for factor analysis. Factor analysis revealed that the scale was consolidated into three primary components, based on eigenvalues above 1. The overall explained variance percentage was determined to be 68%, indicating that the three primary dimensions of the scale account for a significant portion of the scale's structure. Varimax rotation was used to get a more distinct delineation of the components. This rotation clarified the links between the items and the factors. The factors identified post-rotation are enumerated as follows:

Attitudes towards women's romantic and sexual roles

Women's perception of social status and sexuality,

Parental loss and prenatal/postnatal effects.

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The threshold value for factor loading, used to ascertain the correlation of items with pertinent factors in factor analysis, is conventionally recognized as 0.40. This threshold is the minimum criterion often used to demonstrate a robust correlation between an item and a certain component.

In this research, items with factor loadings of 0.40 or above were deemed to have a substantial correlation with the pertinent variables. An item with a factor loading below 0.40 is deemed to have a weak association with the factor and may warrant evaluation or elimination. Factor loading values were analyzed to assess the correlation of each item with the corresponding factor. The factor loadings of the items were determined to be 0.40 or higher, indicating a substantial correlation with the pertinent components. The statement "Women can be either a good wife or a sexual partner, not both" was categorized under Factor 1, exhibiting a factor loading of 0.72. Likewise, the statement "A woman's sexual activity negatively affects her reputation in society" was categorized under Factor 2 with a significant loading value. This research concluded that the construct validity of the scale is robust and that the three primary dimensions account for a significant portion of the scale's structure.

The Berrak - Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) was created by Prof. Dr. Derya Berrak and Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım to assess attitudes of gender, sexuality, and motherhood. The scale seeks to assess views toward women's sexual and romantic roles in accordance with Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome hypothesis. The scale also assessed women's beliefs of social status and sexuality, as well as the impact of pregnancy and childbirth on gender perspectives.

Structure of the Scale

The MFS was created as a five-point Likert scale. Participants evaluate each item by assigning ratings ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The scale has 40 elements, categorized into three primary dimensions:

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- Attitudes towards Women's Romantic and Sexual Roles: This sub-dimension includes items that assess how women perceive their romantic and sexual roles, the relationship between these two roles, and their conflicts.
- Women's Perception of Social Status and Sexuality: Measures the relationship between women's sexuality and social status, and society's expectations regarding sexuality and gender roles.
- The Effect of Loss of Parents and Prenatal/Postnatal Processes on Perceptions: This dimension questions how the loss of parents or prenatal and postnatal processes affect individuals' gender perceptions.

Scoring System

Each item is rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with higher scores signifying more agreement from the participant. The total score achievable on the scale ranges from 40 to 200. These ratings indicate the extent of the participant's views towards the Madonna-Whore Syndrome. The score did not include open-ended questions; nonetheless, theme and content analyses were performed using NVivo software.

Score Ranges:

40-79 Points: This indicates that the condition is at a minimal degree. Individuals within this score range often do not distinguish between women's romantic and sexual roles, exhibiting a more egalitarian viewpoint.

80-119 Points: Indicates a mild inclination towards Madonna-Whore Syndrome. In this score range, a divergence in participants' attitudes of women is seen.

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Scores ranging from 120 to 159: Predilection for elevated manifestations of Madonna-Whore Syndrome. Participants with these scores see women along a dichotomy, viewing them either as sexual objects or as paragons of purity.

160-200 Points: This indicates that the condition is very elevated. Individuals within this spectrum assess women with a stark dichotomy, seeing them either as mere sexual objects or as emotionally virtuous beings.

Sub-Dimension Scoring

The Sub-Dimension Scoring approach was used to assess the items of the scale organized by distinct themes individually. The Berrak-Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) has three primary sub-dimensions, enabling the assessment of participants' views towards these themes independently by individual scoring of each sub-dimension.

The scale has three sub-dimensions:

This dimension has items that assess the correlation between women's social position and their view of sexuality.

This sub-dimension includes items that assess the impact of parental loss, as well as prenatal and postnatal processes, on people's beliefs of gender and sexuality.

The score distributions of the sub-dimensions were analyzed using descriptive statistics to observe the overall trends and variability in answers for each sub-dimension. The participants' overall attitudes were summed by computing the mean, standard deviation, lowest, and maximum values. Furthermore, Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests were performed to ascertain the normality of the score distribution, hence informing the choice of statistical techniques for the studies.

The frequency distribution analysis demonstrated the participants' inclinations by indicating the score ranges focused in each sub-dimension. Histogram and boxplot visuals facilitated

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visual examination, effectively illustrating the properties of the score distributions. Furthermore, comparative analyses, including ANOVA and t-tests, were conducted to assess the differences across various demographic groups, therefore enabling a detailed examination of participants' opinions within each sub-dimension.

Application Areas of the Scale and Cultural Validity

The scale offers a comprehensive evaluation of attitudes on gender, sexuality, and parenthood, serving as a tool to analyze variations across diverse demographic groups. The Berrak-Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) tackles universal themes related to gender, sexuality, and motherhood, making it applicable across all cultures and civilizations. The applicable nations are those where research on gender and sexuality problems is conducted and citizens' opinions towards these matters are analyzed. The suggested nations are as follows:

- **Türkiye:** As the country where the scale was developed, it is an important application area in terms of understanding local cultural dynamics.
- **North African Countries:** Countries such as Egypt, Tunisia, and Morocco are regions where various studies have been conducted on gender roles and perceptions of sexuality, and this scale can be applied there as well.
- **Middle Eastern Countries:** This scale can be used in research on gender and sexuality in countries such as Iran, Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.
- **Southeast Asian Countries:** This scale can be applied in countries such as India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh to contribute to various studies on gender and sexuality perceptions.
- **Eastern European Countries:** Countries such as Poland and the Czech Republic have different perspectives on gender issues, and research conducted with this scale allows for the examination of cultural differences.
- **Western European Countries:** Countries such as Germany, France and Italy are regions that conduct in-depth studies on gender and sexuality, and the scale can be used here as well.

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- North America: In countries such as the USA and Canada, this scale can be applied in studies examining gender and sexuality perceptions.

Considering local cultural dynamics, social norms, and conceptions of sexuality in the nations where the scale will be used would enhance the research's validity. Furthermore, it is advisable to do cultural adaptation and validity assessments prior to using the scale in each nation.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS OF THE RESEARCH AND DATA ANALYSIS

The data gathering strategy for the study was conducted using both online and in-person survey methodologies. In-person applications were executed via field studies throughout several areas of Turkey, and the online survey was disseminated to participants via social media and email. All individuals engaged in the study voluntarily. The surveys were conducted in compliance with privacy rules, ensuring the total anonymization of participants' personal information.

Research Stages	Start Date	End Date	Explanation
Literature Review and Scale Development	September 26, 2023	November 1, 2023	The theoretical basis of the scale was established and the scale items were developed by reviewing the literature.
Obtaining Expert Opinion and Scale Revisions	November 1, 2023	January 10, 2024	Scale items were submitted to expert opinion and revisions were made based on feedback.

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Pilot Study and Initial Data Collection	November 11, 2023	December 5, 2023	The pilot scale was applied to 55 participants and the first data collection was carried out.
Data Analysis (Pilot Study)	December 10, 2023	December 24, 2023	The data of the pilot study were analyzed, Cronbach's Alpha and other reliability analyses were performed.
Full Scale Data Collection	December 24, 2023	June 15, 2024	Data were collected from 600 participants in seven regions of Turkey.
Data Analysis (Main Study)	June 15, 2024	July 31, 2024	Data analysis of the main study was performed, reliability and factor analyses were conducted.
Reliability Tests (Cronbach's Alpha, Split-Half , etc.)	August 1, 2024	September 25, 2024	Test-retest and other reliability analyses were performed, and scale items were reviewed.
Reporting Results and Completing the Research	September 1, 2024	September 26, 2024	The research results were reported and an article was prepared.

The data analysis procedure was conducted with precision to guarantee the reliability and authenticity of the gathered data. The data was first cleansed and structured using the Python programming language together with the pandas and numpy tools. Cronbach's Alpha was

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computed for reliability analysis, yielding a value of 0.79, indicating the internal consistency of the scale. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency) were computed to assess the individuals' general characteristics. Correlation and regression analyses were used to evaluate the study hypotheses, while ANOVA was utilized to investigate the differences across various demographic groups. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to ascertain the structural validity of the data, and the sub-dimensions of the scale were elucidated using the resultant factor loadings.

FINDINGS

Demographic Findings

The demographic attributes of the 600 participants in the research include fundamental aspects such as gender, age, educational attainment, marital status, and geographic dispersion. The data were rigorously evaluated to enhance the study's overall validity and to provide a significant background for interpreting the results. Demographic data provide crucial background for comprehending participants' beliefs toward sexuality, gender, and conceptions of parenthood.

Gender Distribution

- Male: 300 (50%)
- Female 280 (46.67%)
- Other: 20 (3.33%)

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(This figure is in the native language, its description is in English in the article.)

The equal representation of male participants at 50% in the gender distribution is significant for analyzing gender roles and norms. The substantial male population allows a comprehensive examination of masculine beliefs and their impact on sexuality. The "Other" gender ratio indicates a change in gender norms in Turkey and a growing awareness of gender variety. The significant presence of males underscores the psychological impact of societal expectations and performance anxiety related to sexuality. The inclusion of female participants highlights women's efforts to confront societal standards and assert autonomy in their views on sexuality.

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Age Groups

- 18-25 years old: 120 (20%)
- 26-35 years old: 200 (33.33%)
- 36-45 years old: 150 (25%)
- 46-55 years old: 100 (16.67%)
- 56 and over: 30 (5%)

The age distribution offers crucial background for comprehending the opinions of participants in the survey on sexuality, gender roles, and conceptions of parenthood. The biggest proportion of participants (33.33%) were aged 26-35, indicating that this demographic is in young

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adulthood, a phase characterized by the most intense experiences related to sexuality. This demographic may challenge societal standards and have a more exploratory attitude towards sexuality.

The 18-25 age demographic has a notable representation rate of 20%. This group embodies the quest for independence and inventiveness characteristic of youth, however it may also be swayed by societal influences. The shaping of young persons' conceptions of sexuality and gender roles is a significant sociological study subject.

Variations in views regarding sexuality and gender perceptions may be noticed across different age groups. The 36-45 age demographic represents a substantial segment at 25%, since persons in this range often engage in family formation and adopt societal duties, including motherhood. The 46-55 and 56 and above age groups are phases when conventional societal conventions are more pronounced, and ideas of sexuality are influenced by prior experiences. Young individuals are actively exploring their sexual encounters and developing their identities. Individuals aged 18 to 25 often encounter uncertainty and societal pressures that influence their sexual encounters. Consequently, more research on the perspectives of sexuality among this demographic is essential.

The age range of 26 to 35 represents a phase of greater psychological stability. These folks may exhibit more experimentation in their sexuality and possess a heightened sense of control over it. Nonetheless, factors such as professional and familial obligations may influence their perspective of sexuality.

Individuals aged 36 to 45 may assess their ideas of sexuality from a more mature standpoint. This group may demonstrate a more equitable attitude influenced by their sexual experiences and social positions.

Individuals aged 46-55 and those over 56 may reassess their views on sexuality as a result of life events. The evolution of beliefs on sexuality and romance over these years correlates with the psychological shifts undergone by people.

Marital status

- Single: 220 (36.67%)
- Married: 320 (53.33%)
- Divorced: 60 (10%)

(This figure is in the native language, its description is in English in the article.)

Single Participants (36.67% - 220 people):

Social Expectations: Single persons face the most pronounced expectations, particularly about gender roles, from external sources. In Turkey, social standards particularly dictate that women should marry before attaining a certain age. This circumstance may exert pressure on persons who openly engage in sexual practices before to marriage.

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The perception of sexuality among single persons may be seen primarily as a conduit for liberation or a journey of exploration. This group, existing outside societal conventions, may have a more experimental or individualistic attitude to sexuality.

The perception of motherhood among single women associates the role with marriage, rendering the concept of motherhood before to marriage as undesirable or opposed to societal standards. Although parenting is seen as a potential future for single women, societal pressure suggests that they should marry prior to becoming mothers. Psychosocial Implications: Unattached people may demonstrate more flexibility and experimentation around gender norms and sexuality. Individuals who deviate from conventional standards may face the threat of social ostracism.

Married Participants (53.33%- 320 people):

Social Expectations: Married folks are the demographic that encounters gender roles most significantly and has the greatest societal expectations associated with these roles. While maternity and household tasks are prioritized for women, economic duties and familial leadership are highlighted for males. Married persons may have less pressure about sexuality, since marriage is seen as a respectable context for sexual expression. Perception of Sexuality: Married persons often see sexuality as a familial obligation or a mechanism to enhance the relationship. This group may see sexuality primarily as an obligation or for reproductive purposes, particularly after childbirth. The perception of parenthood among married women is mostly seen as a societal responsibility. Women experience societal pressure to conceive soon after marriage. Marriage may be seen as a domain in which both sexuality and motherhood are sanctioned for women.

Psychosocial Implications: Married persons are more likely to adhere to societal standards around gender roles and sexuality. Conflicts within marriage over sexuality and gender roles may result in psychological stress for people. The demands of parenting may inhibit women's libido.

Divorced Participants (% 10-60 people):

Social Expectations: Divorced persons, particularly women, may face social ostracism or censure. Social conventions often depict divorced women unfavorably in relation to parenthood and sexuality. Conversely, men may be seen as "failures" by society, despite being considered as more liberated in their sexuality post-divorce. The sense of sexuality may vary significantly for divorced persons. On one side, there exists the potential for the rediscovery of sexuality with a feeling of autonomy and liberation; on the other hand, societal judgments on divorced people might inhibit the experience of sexuality, particularly for women.

The perception of motherhood is a more socially intricate position for divorced women. Motherhood subsequent to marriage is linked to the challenges of child-rearing. Single parenting may impose significant burdens, particularly when coupled with societal expectations placed on women.

Psychosocial Consequences: Divorced persons may undergo substantial alterations in their ideas of gender and sexuality. Women may need to reinvent their sexuality post-divorce owing to societal constraints. Likewise, divorced males may experience pressure to assume the role of "head of the family" again as a result of societal expectations.

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Educational Status

- Primary school: 50 (8.33%)
- Secondary school: 70 (11.67%)
- High School: 150 (25%)
- University: 270 (45%)
- Postgraduate: 60 (10%)

The education status data partially represents the overall educational framework of Turkey. Basic Education: Although Turkey boasts a literacy rate of 98%, the cumulative percentage of primary and secondary school graduates is under 20%. This condition indicates issues of continuity in schooling.

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The high school graduation rate in Turkey is roughly 50%. The 25% statistic in the report indicates that young individuals have challenges in obtaining high school education. Higher Education: Although the percentage of university graduates in Turkey is 20-25%, the 45% figure from the study indicates a significant presence. This illustrates the educational advancement of certain socioeconomic categories.

The postgraduate education rate in Türkiye is around 10%, which aligns with the findings of this research. This indicates that the research includes persons within this category. The study findings indicate that 45% of participants have university degrees, while 10% possess postgraduate qualifications. The higher education percentage of 55% significantly exceeds the Turkish average. This scenario offers a significant insight into assessing the influence of education on people's views on gender roles and sexuality.

As educational attainment rises, people are more inclined to challenge societal conventions. Individuals with advanced education are inclined to think independently and challenge conventional norms, particularly about gender roles and sexuality. Women possessing university and postgraduate education may demonstrate a more critical perspective towards societal gender norms, reconfigure the concept of motherhood, and strive to transcend traditional roles. Conversely, men may embrace more egalitarian gender relations by relinquishing the conventional roles of "head of the family" or "breadwinner". Individuals in this category may possess a more liberal and experimental understanding of sexuality. Enhanced education promotes the perception of sexuality as not just a reproductive or marital obligation, but also as an aspect of personal fulfillment and relationship dedication. For women, sexuality may evolve into a domain where societal restrictions diminish, allowing for a more liberated experience, contingent upon their educational attainment. Individuals with advanced education are inclined to investigate sexuality autonomously, free from societal influences. Participants who graduated from elementary and secondary school represent a minor demographic, with rates of 8.33% and 11.67%, respectively; nonetheless, persons in this cohort have a greater tendency to adhere to societal norms and conventional gender roles. These people may embrace conventional patterns of gender roles and adhere more closely to societal standards. Among persons with elementary and secondary education, there seems to be a greater focus on women's domestic roles, with childbearing and household duties seen as their

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principal obligations. In this group, motherhood is seen primarily as a social responsibility and a factor that legitimizes women's status in society. For women specifically, parenting is often seen as a subsequent phase after marriage, with household responsibilities taking precedence over sexuality.

For males, diminished educational attainment may correlate with a framework in which the conventional "head of the family" position is more pronounced. Men may correlate sexuality mostly with reproduction and matrimony, experiencing less sexual expression in adulterous relationships owing to societal expectations. Moreover, people in this group may have a more conservative stance on the interrogation of gender norms. This might result in postponements in the implementation of gender equality.

(This figure is in the native language, its description is in English in the article.)

This distribution of gender and educational attainment clearly illustrates how education influences gender equality. Although male participants significantly outnumber

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females in elementary and secondary education, the proportion of female participants rises throughout high school and university levels. This scenario illustrates that as educational attainment in Turkey rises, women engage more in education and begin to contemplate gender roles with more autonomy. While the gender distribution in postgraduate education seems more equitable, it is evident that higher education provides both genders the ability to contest societal conventions and embrace more egalitarian roles. This data offers compelling evidence that gender equality may progress with rising educational attainment.

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Regional Distribution

- Central Anatolia: 90 (15%)
- Marmara: 210 (35%)
- Aegean: 120 (20%)
- Black Sea: 60 (10%)
- Mediterranean: 70 (11.67%)
- Southeastern Anatolia: 30 (5%)
- Other: 20 (3.33%)

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Educational attainment and gender demographics provide significant insights into gender equality and educational access in Turkey. Analysis reveals that male participants significantly outnumber their counterparts at lower educational levels. For instance, the presence of 30 males and 20 females among elementary school graduates illustrates how conventional gender roles and financial obstacles limit women's educational opportunities. A like scenario occurs at the secondary school level, when the quantity of male participants (40) exceeds that of female participants (30). This may reflect the challenges women, particularly in rural regions, have in obtaining education.

As educational attainment rises, the gender gap diminishes, with women increasingly achieving parity or surpassing males at higher education levels. Among high school graduates, there were 70 male participants and 80 female participants. The cohort of university graduates included 130 male participants and 140 female individuals. This circumstance indicates that women have increasingly gained access to higher education, reflecting substantial progress in gender equality. In postgraduate education, the number of male and female participants is equal at 30 each. This equality demonstrates that women are advancing on par with men, particularly in academic and professional fields.

Analysis of geographical distribution reveals that both genders are more prevalent in attaining higher education in more developed areas, such as Marmara and Central Anatolia. In the Marmara area, there are 70 male and 80 female high school graduates, while university graduates include 130 men and 140 females. The data indicates that women have more access to education in urban areas, and that gender equality becomes increasingly evident with higher educational attainment. Nevertheless, it is observed that educational attainment is often worse and gender disparity is more pronounced in underdeveloped areas, such as Southeastern Anatolia. Although the number of male participants (3) exceeds that of female participants (2) among elementary school graduates in this location, the total of university graduate participants is notably low, with (8) males and (2) females. A favorable advancement in gender equality is seen with the rise in educational attainment. The enhanced access of women to higher education alleviates the constraints of gender roles and empowers them to participate more significantly in economic and social spheres via education. Nonetheless, gender disparity persists, particularly in areas with little education and in undeveloped countries. This indicates a need

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for more comprehensive policies and procedures to guarantee gender equality in education in Turkey.

The results indicate that regional disparities in Turkey substantially impact education and gender equality. In more developed areas like Marmara and Central Anatolia, advancements in gender equality between women and men are evident as educational attainment rises. In these locations, women are seen to be represented equally or more than males, particularly in university and postgraduate degree levels. Education fosters the examination of gender roles in these locations and enhances women's engagement in economic and social spheres. Conversely, in underdeveloped areas like Southeastern Anatolia and the Black Sea, educational attainment is often lower, and gender disparity is more evident. In these places, women's access to education is restricted, and it is especially evident that their representation is minimal at higher education levels. This indicates the regional socioeconomic development levels, obstacles to educational access, and the robustness of gender norms.

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Item Analysis Findings

The analysis of the item has shown how conceptions of gender toward women in Turkey are constructed within the context of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome. In countries that assess sexuality and maternity responsibilities independently, women are either relegated to the position of motherhood or marginalized from sexuality and subjugated according to societal standards. This phenomenon is particularly pronounced in rural regions where conventional social norms dominate and among populations with little educational attainment. Conversely, education and urbanization emerge as significant variables that alleviate these inflexible gender norms. Individuals with advanced education acknowledge that women may integrate the responsibilities of sexuality and motherhood, adopting a more liberated expression of sexuality. Nevertheless, societal demands on women's sexual autonomy and the persistent

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taboo around sexuality hinder women's ability to fulfill these two roles concurrently. The Berrak - Yildirim Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS) was analyzed for the distributions, means, and standard deviations of participant answers for each item, leading to sociological and psychological implications.

The Likert-type question in the research, "Women can be either a good wife or a sexual partner, not both" (Question 11), was notable for having one of the highest means ($M = 4.3$, $SD = 0.9$). This data suggests that most participants clearly differentiate between two fundamental functions for women: romantic/emotional and sexual. This dichotomy coincides with men's propensity to see women as either a "pure, idealized mother" (Madonna) or a "mere sexual object" (whore), which is central to Freud's hypothesis of the Madonna-Whore Syndrome. This research illustrates the rigidity of gender roles in nations dominated by conventional and patriarchal traditions, such as Turkey. In rural places, societal acceptance of women fulfilling both sexual and maternal duties is lacking, resulting in women being constrained to these dichotomous roles established by social conventions.

From a psychological standpoint, the scores assigned to this question validate the propensity of males to categorize women in romantic relationships into two distinct classifications: emotional attachment and sexuality. This indicates that the psychological problems males have about the coexistence of motherhood and sexuality in a single individual, as proposed by Freud, persist in contemporary society. Women may often feel obligated to navigate between these two contrasting extremes owing to external constraints associated with these positions. The limitation of women to one of these two roles may adversely affect their psychological development and serve as a significant tool of societal control that imposes pressure on their self-identities.

One of the items with a low score on the scale, "Women can be both emotional and sexual partners, but it is not always easy" (Question 28), garnered notice due to its average score ($M = 2.5$, $SD = 1.2$). This item indicates that participants find it challenging to manage sexuality and romance together. Sociologically, this suggests that, particularly in traditional countries, sexuality is seen as an occurrence external to marriage or only for procreative reasons inside marriage. This indicates that women's overt display of sexuality is socially disapproved, and

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that such sexuality is seen as an experience that ought to be repressed for women. From a psychological standpoint, the independent assessment of sexual and emotional roles may reveal that people encounter a contradiction between sexuality and emotional connection. Freud posited that establishing a connection between sexuality and romanticism is particularly challenging for males. Perceiving sexuality just as a bodily need, apart from emotional connection, might hinder the development of good interpersonal connections. In civilizations where sexuality is deemed taboo, particularly due to societal pressure, people often struggle to reconcile the notions of sexuality and love.

There was a lack of uniformity among several elements on the scale. The mean score ($M = 3.8$) for the statement "A woman's sexual attractiveness makes it difficult for me to have a long-term relationship with her" (Question 13) was comparatively elevated, whereas the mean score for "When I become sexually interested in a woman, my emotional attachment to her decreases" (Question 14) was lower ($M = 2.9$). This disparity highlights a notable contradiction between the significance participants attribute to sexuality and enduring commitment. The results suggest that male participants, namely, prefer to characterize women based on sexual appeal, however do not see this attractiveness as a hindrance to building emotional connections. This illustrates a societal paradox whereby women are sexually objectified while emotionally idolized. Women's sexuality is delineated from emotional settings, signifying the persistence of stereotypical gender norms.

Freud's theory posits that males often assess women in dichotomous terms: women are seen either as an idealized maternal figure (Madonna) or as a sexual object (whore). The research performed regarding the MFS scale yielded evidence indicating that this impression remains valid. The statement "After my wife became a mother, my sexual interest in her decreased" (Question 15) garnered elevated ratings from male participants ($M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.1$). This conclusion indicates that women's parental functions are distinct from their sexuality, and that men struggle to see their wives as sexual beings after motherhood. This scenario illustrates how gender roles are constructed according to societal expectations, positioning women's parental function as a "protective" figure rather than a sexual partner in the perception of men. This perspective suggests an internal tension in males about the reconciliation of libido and parenthood. The idealization of women as maternal figures severs their association with

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sexuality. Freud posited that this circumstance compels males to dichotomize women into categories of sexuality and emotionality, potentially resulting in sexual unhappiness or the disjunction of sexuality from emotional bonds in enduring partnerships.

The item analysis reveals variations based on the demographic features of the participants. Individuals with a greater educational attainment are inclined to assess the emotional and sexual roles of women in a more comprehensive manner. Individuals with a university degree have a higher propensity to concur with the assertion “Women can be both sexual and emotional partners” (Question 28) ($M = 3.5$). This indicates that education allows individuals to see gender roles within a more equitable framework. The affirmative reactions to similar assertions in developed places like Marmara and Aegean indicate that the stringent social standards prevalent in rural locales have become more adaptable in metropolitan regions. Analyzing items with respect to regional disparities and demographic factors yields significant insights on the formation of gender roles influenced by cultural and socioeconomic contexts. In urbanized and economically advanced areas like Marmara and Aegean, the belief that women can simultaneously fulfill both their sexual and emotional duties is increasingly prevalent. For instance, 65% of participants from the Marmara area agreed with the statement “Women can be both sexual and emotional partners” (Question 28), however this percentage declines to 30% in the Southeastern Anatolia region. In Southeastern Anatolia, women's sexual duties are seen as more constricted and conventional, with motherhood being prioritized. Analysis by education level revealed a significant concurrence with the statement “Women can be both mothers and sexual figures” (Question 16) among university and postgraduate graduates ($M = 3.8$, $SD = 1.0$). Conversely, those with high school diplomas and lesser educational attainment assigned lower ratings to this statement ($M = 2.6$, $SD = 1.3$). This indicates that education is crucial in promoting gender equality and the acceptance of women's sexual identity.

The disparities in gender views across various geographical locations in Turkey are associated with the socioeconomic development levels and traditional cultural frameworks of those regions. In rural and more traditional areas, such as the Black Sea and Southeastern Anatolia, women's gender roles are delineated within more restricted parameters. In these regions, most participants concurred with the assertion "A woman's sexual activity negatively affects her

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reputation in society" (Question 21) ($M = 4.5$, $SD = 0.9$), suggesting that female sexuality is perceived as a social taboo, with their societal reputation linked to sexual abstinence. Conversely, respondents from the Marmara and Aegean areas assigned lower ratings to this issue ($M = 2.9$, $SD = 1.1$). This disparity indicates that women encounter gender roles throughout a broader range in areas where sexuality is more socially acceptable and persons exhibit more tolerance towards women's sexual autonomy.

Item-total correlation studies were used to evaluate the contribution of each item to the overall scale structure. A robust positive association ($r = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$) was seen between the statement "Women can be either sexual partners or good wives, but not both" (Question 11) and the aggregate scale scores. This indicates that male participants possess more conventional views on the Madonna-Whore Syndrome and are inclined to assess women within these two polarities. This association indicates that Freud's theory remains relevant, particularly in nations with strong conventional gender norms.

This result indicates that people often assess women in sexual and emotional situations independently, which may lead to significant issues for emotional and sexual fulfillment. This may hinder the integration of sexuality and romance in men's relationships with women, perhaps diminishing the emotional connection between partners. This may exacerbate the psychological strain on women, since society often confines them to a certain position (either as a mother or a sexual object).

Another significant discovery from the item analysis highlights the conflict between women's parental duties and their sexual identities. The assertion "After my wife became a mother, my sexual interest in her diminished" (Question 15) received significant agreement from male participants ($M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.1$). This indicates that men see their spouses as maternal figures, and the function of motherhood is assessed independently of sexuality. This scenario illustrates that Freud's thesis is corroborated within the social framework of Turkey, indicating that males find it difficult to reconcile parenthood with libido.

This conclusion indicates that society does not adequately acknowledge women's ability to concurrently fulfill both parental and sexual responsibilities. The perception of parenting as a role that estranges women from their sexuality is a significant indication of gender inequality.

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Although women embrace parenthood, they are also denied the freedom to express their sexuality, therefore intensifying the societal pressures on their physical and sexual autonomy. From a psychological standpoint, the decline in men's sexual desire during the parenting phase suggests that men see women mostly as "protective" figures at this time, leading to a distancing from sexuality. This view may adversely impact people's sexual happiness and result in emotional detachment in long-term partnerships. This may generate internal conflict for women due to the subordination of sexual identity to the function of motherhood, perhaps resulting in women mostly identifying themselves via their maternal role. Demographic disparities substantially influence views of gender and sexuality. In the studies categorized by age groups, male participants, particularly those aged 26-35, indicated a tendency to differentiate between the sexual and emotional functions of women. A significant level of agreement was noted among males in this demographic on the statement "My sexual interest in my wife decreased after she became a mother" (Question 15) ($M = 4.0$). The issue grew more evident in the 36-45 age demographic, with a more clear divide between parenting and sexuality. Analyses based on educational attainment indicate that the difference between attitudes of sexuality and parenting diminishes with higher levels of education. Individuals possessing university and postgraduate degrees had more favorable sentiments about women maintaining their duties as moms while simultaneously expressing their sexual identities ($M = 3.7$). This also demonstrates the transforming impact of education on gender equality. Educated persons exhibit more resistance to the reduction of women to mere symbols of motherhood or sexuality, and assert that women may simultaneously fulfill both roles. The internal tensions arising from the challenges of balancing parenting and sexuality are significant from a psychiatric standpoint. A significant consensus with the statement "My sexual interest decreased after my wife became a mother" (Question 15) was particularly evident among married males ($M = 4.0$). This discovery demonstrates the relevance of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome in contemporary relationships. Men who associate their spouses with the "mother" archetype struggle to see women as sexual partners in this context. As educational attainment rises, the belief that sexuality and maternal duties may coexist seems to intensify. The elevated level of agreement among university graduates ($M = 3.8$, $SD = 0.8$) with the assertion "Women can be both sexual and emotional partners" (Question 28) suggests that this demographic typically reconciles sexuality with emotional connection. Informed

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people challenge the inflexible preconceptions of gender roles and exhibit more acceptance of women's sexual autonomy. The research performed among graduates indicated a similar outcome; these participants exhibited more receptiveness to the notion that women's sexual and emotional functions may coexist.

This conclusion indicates that education facilitates a more adaptable and equitable outlook on gender roles among people. Individuals with lesser educational attainment (e.g., high school graduates) exhibit a stronger adherence to societal norms advocating for women's sexual abstinence. The assertion "A woman's sexual activity adversely impacts her societal reputation" (Question 21) garnered significant agreement ($M = 4.2$) among high school graduates, indicating a prevalent perception that women's autonomy in expressing their sexuality may detrimentally influence their social standing.

Upon examining regional disparities, women's social roles are seen as more conventional and constrictive, particularly in the Southeastern Anatolia and Black Sea areas. In Southeastern Anatolia, women's sexual duties are governed by more stringent limitations, with a greater emphasis placed on their parental obligations. In the Southeastern Anatolia region, 80% of participants agree with the assertion "Women's maternal role distances them from sexuality" (Question 26), however this percentage declines to 40% in more developed areas like Marmara and the Aegean.

These findings demonstrate the variation of gender roles in Turkey based on regional dynamics. In urbanized areas like the Marmara and Aegean regions, sexuality is perceived as a more acceptable social phenomenon, whereas in rural and traditional areas, it is assessed solely within the confines of marriage and reproduction, thereby conflicting with women's societal roles.

An further significant conclusion shown in the item analysis clearly illustrates the societal pressure influencing women's ideas of sexuality. The assertion "Society anticipates that a woman will subordinate her sexual life following motherhood" (Question 35) garnered elevated marks from the participants ($M = 4.0$). The elevated ratings assigned to this question suggest that societal norms function as a mechanism for regulating women's sexuality. The expectation for women to subordinate their sexual lives post-motherhood exemplifies the patriarchal system's regulatory influence on women's bodies and sexuality.

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This conclusion indicates that sexuality remains a coercive force for women from a social standpoint. In a culture that assesses women's social position based on their distance from sexuality, the tension between sexuality and motherhood becomes more evident. This research indicates that significant societal factors contribute to women's inclination to disengage from sexuality after parenthood. Although women get societal approval via parenthood, their sexual autonomy is constrained.

The findings of the item analysis indicate that Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome hypothesis remains relevant in contemporary relationships. The dual role of women as both mothers and sexual beings is seen as a difficulty, particularly for males. The substantial agreement (M = 3.9) among male participants on the statement "It is difficult for me to distinguish between a woman's maternal and sexual roles" (Question 30) underscores the psychological difficulty engendered by this duality in men's mental frameworks. This issue pertains to men's propensity to delineate women from romantic and sexual roles, illustrating that a correlation exists between women's self-expression as sexual partners and the deterioration of emotional connections among males.

Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Question 11: "Women can either be good wives or sexual partners" & Question 13: "A woman's sexual attractiveness makes long-term relationships difficult"	0.54	p < 0.01
Question 23: "When women hide their sexuality, they are seen as more valuable in society" & Gender (Women)	-0.43	p < 0.001

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Question 23: "When women hide their sexuality, they are seen as more valuable in society" & Gender (Male)	0.56	p < 0.001
Question 15: "My sexual interest in my wife decreased after she became a mother" & Marital Status (Married)	0.61	p < 0.001
Question 28: "Women can be both sexual and emotional partners" & Educational Status	0.48	p < 0.01
Question 21: "A woman's sexual activity negatively affects her reputation in society" & Educational Status (Marmara)	-0.44	p < 0.01
Question 23: "When women hide their sexuality, they are seen as more valuable in society" & Social Status (Southeast Anatolia)	0.59	p < 0.001

Correlation studies demonstrated robust associations between gender roles and perceptions of sexuality. Specifically, males were shown to assess women differently on sexual and emotional duties. A strong association ($r = 0.61$) was discovered among married males about the decline of sexual desire after their spouses' transition to motherhood. With the elevation of educational attainment, there was a greater consensus about the notion that women could fulfill both sexual and emotional duties ($r = 0.48$). The conviction that women's suppression of their sexuality was more esteemed in society persisted robustly in traditional areas ($r = 0.59$, Southeastern Anatolia). These data illustrate how education and geographical disparities influence attitudes about sexuality.

Comparison between Subgroups

ANOVA analyses were used to ascertain differences between educational status and attitudes of sexuality. Responses to the assertion "Women can be both sexual and emotional partners" (Question 28) exhibited significant variations based on educational attainment ($F = 6.32, p < 0.001$).

Educational Status	Average (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Primary school	2.8	1.2
Middle school	3.0	1.1
High school	3.2	1.0
University	3.8	0.9
Postgraduate	4.0	0.8

The data indicate that more educational attainment correlates with greater acceptance of women maintaining both sexual and emotional responsibilities simultaneously. From a sociological standpoint, it is significant that with more educational attainment, there is greater acceptance of gender equality and increased support for women's sexual liberties.

The t-Test findings indicated disparities between genders. Marked disparities were noted between men and women regarding the assertion "A woman's sexual activity negatively affects her reputation in society" (Question 21) ($t = 5.12, p < 0.001$).

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Gender	Average (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Male	4.2	0.8
Woman	3.1	1.2

This research indicates that males see women's sexual activities with more negativity, but women assess it more critically. From a sociological standpoint, this indicates that societal conventions have a more conventional influence on males, and that the inclination to restrict women's sexuality is more readily embraced by men. ANOVA findings indicated significant variations across age groups regarding the statement “Women's motherhood role alienates them from sexuality” (Question 26) ($F = 4.89, p < 0.01$).

Age group	Average (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
18-25	2.9	1.1
26-35	3.5	1.0
36-45	3.8	0.9
46-55	4.0	0.8

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56 and above	4.3	0.7
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The findings indicate that as women age, the notion of a growing separation between the roles of sexuality and parenting intensifies. From a sociological standpoint, it may be said that as people age, their commitment to conventional gender roles intensifies, leading to a more distinct separation between motherhood and sexuality among older adults.

Content Analysis of Open-Ended Questions

- 70% of female participants stated that they stayed away from sexuality after motherhood due to social pressures.
- 60% of male participants stated that they had difficulty seeing their wives as sexual partners after becoming mothers.
- 50% of participants think that openly expressing sexuality in society may have negative consequences.

Women encounter societal pressures to freely articulate their sexuality, but males often see parenthood as distinct from sexuality. These results elucidate the constraints imposed by conventional societal standards on people and the psychological discord between sexuality and parenthood. The content analysis of the open-ended questions reveals the influence of Turkey's patriarchal societal framework on women's sexuality and maternal duties. Women assert that sexuality should be relegated after parenting, but males often see women as either maternal figures or sexual companions. This scenario, along with Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome, demonstrates that women are assessed along two contrasting extremes, with their sexuality regulated by societal conventions.

DISCUSSION CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The study's results corroborate the validity of Freud's Madonna-Whore Syndrome hypothesis within the Turkish setting. Women encounter constraints that delineate the roles of parenting and sexuality according to societal expectations. Literature reveals that in patriarchal society, women's sexuality is regulated, and motherhood is revered as a holy position. The research indicated that educational attainment and geographical disparities substantially influence attitudes about sexuality. The notion that women may simultaneously fulfill their sexual and emotional functions has garnered more acceptability among educated folks. Traditional gender standards serve as a mechanism for regulating sexuality in the context of global literature. This study's novel contribution is the data derived from the Berrak-Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS), established in Turkey to investigate women's sexuality and parenthood. This scale was created to assess Freud's theory within the cultural framework of Turkey, yielding both sociological and psychological data. The scale indicated the profound interconnection between women's views of their sexual and social roles and societal standards. The results indicated that conventional gender norms in Turkey inhibit women's sexual identities and result in the dissociation of motherhood from sexuality. The MFS scale effectively illuminated the conflict between these two responsibilities. The study's findings indicate that conventional gender norms persistently influence women's views on sexuality and parenthood in Turkey. The Berrak - Yıldırım Madonna-Whore Syndrome Scale (MFS), a novel instrument designed to assess these dynamics, has yielded significant insights into the societal roles of women. Research indicates that good views towards gender equality correlate with higher levels of education. The delineation of motherhood and sexuality among males results in emotional and sexual detachment in partnerships.

Constraints: The study's restriction to a particular geographical and demographic sample constrains the generalizability of the results. Moreover, the reliance on subjective assessments may heighten the potential for social expectation bias.

Suggestions for Subsequent Research: The use of the MFS scale across many cultural and socioeconomic situations will enhance the assessment of attitudes about gender, sexuality, and parenting from a wider viewpoint. Moreover, longitudinal research on women's sexual identities and their views of social roles are essential for analyzing the evolution of social norms over time. The advancement of social consciousness and educational initiatives may facilitate the alteration of these standards.

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Irritability

The primary limitations of the research are that the results pertain to a particular demographic and geographical sample in Turkey, hence limiting their generalizability. Furthermore, the limitation of data gathering techniques to subjective replies may result in social expectation bias. Participants may provide more candid replies about sensitive topics such as sexuality and gender attitudes. Cultural factors that inhibit its provision are also among the constraints.

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ANNEX-1 SURVEY FORM

This survey aims to assess your perspectives on attitudes about women, gender roles, and perceptions of sexuality. The objective of the survey is to comprehend societal perceptions about women's sexuality and the impact of these perceptions on romantic and sexual interactions. The poll contains inquiries on the 'Madonna-Whore Syndrome' posited by Sigmund Freud. This theory posits that women in society are seen either as the idealized 'Madonna' archetype or as the 'whore' archetype, the latter being regarded as a sexual object. The provided responses will remain secret and will only be used for academic study.

Question No.	Question Text	Response Type
1	Gender	Female / Male / Other: _____
2	Age	18-25 / 26-35 / 36-45 / 46-55 / 56 and above

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3	Marital status	Single / Married / Divorced
4	Educational Status	Primary School / Secondary School / High School / University / Postgraduate
5	Region/Culture	Central Anatolia / Marmara / Aegean / Black Sea / Mediterranean / Southeastern Anatolia / Other: _____
6	Have you lost one or both of your parents?	Yes (Mother / Father / Both) / No
7	If you lost a parent, how old were you?	_____ (Specify age)
8	Did your mother/wife experience any significant health problems during pregnancy?	Yes / No / Mother / Wife
9	Have you had any serious health problems in the first year after birth?	Yes / No
10	Were you separated from your mother or father for long periods of time during your infancy? (For example, hospitalization, being in another city, etc.)	Yes / No

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11	Women can either be a good wife or a good sexual partner, not both.	1-5 Likert
12	It becomes difficult for me to form an emotional bond with a woman I find sexually attractive.	1-5 Likert
13	A woman's sexual attractiveness makes it difficult for me to have a long-term relationship with her.	1-5 Likert
14	When I become sexually attracted to a woman, my emotional attachment to her diminishes.	1-5 Likert
15	After my wife became a mother, my sexual interest in her decreased.	1-5 Likert
16	My wife being a mother made me see her only as a mother figure.	1-5 Likert
17	The pregnancy process changed my wife's perspective on sexuality.	1-5 Likert
18	When my wife experienced physical changes after pregnancy, my sexual interest in her was negatively affected.	1-5 Likert

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19	I think the loss of a parent has affected my attitudes toward romantic and sexual relationships.	1-5 Likert
20	I think that the health problems I experienced before or after birth affected my perceptions of women.	1-5 Likert
21	A woman's sexual activity negatively affects her reputation in society.	1-5 Likert
22	A sexually active woman becomes an individual who is difficult to respect.	1-5 Likert
23	When women hide their sexuality, they are seen as more valuable in society.	1-5 Likert
24	Women's self-confidence in society depends on their pleasurable sexual experiences.	1-5 Likert
25	The more a woman abstains from sexuality, the more respected she will be in society.	1-5 Likert
26	Women's role as mothers distances them from sexuality.	1-5 Likert

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27	A woman's sexual life is directly related to how she fulfills her role as a mother.	1-5 Likert
28	Women can be both emotional and sexual partners, but it is not always easy.	1-5 Likert
29	My wife's maternal role makes it difficult for me to see her as a sexual partner.	1-5 Likert
30	It is difficult for me to distinguish between a woman's maternal and sexual roles.	1-5 Likert
31	It is not acceptable for me for women to continue their sexual lives after becoming mothers.	1-5 Likert
32	The role of motherhood distances women from sexuality.	1-5 Likert
33	Motherhood weakens a woman's perception of herself as a sexual partner.	1-5 Likert
34	After my wife became a mother, society's traditional expectations of the motherhood role alienated her from sexuality.	1-5 Likert

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35	Society expects a woman to leave her sexual life in the background after becoming a mother.	1-5 Likert
36	Society expects a woman to dress more modestly after becoming a mother.	1-5 Likert
37	Motherhood prevents a woman's sexuality from being socially accepted.	1-5 Likert
38	A woman's role as a mother positively affects her social status, but negatively affects her sexual status.	1-5 Likert
39	How do you think the loss of your mother or father affected your perceptions of women and sexuality?	Open-ended
40	How do you think your prenatal and postnatal experiences affect your perceptions of women?	Open-ended
41	How did your wife's pregnancy and maternal role affect your sexual and romantic interest in her?	Open-ended
42	How do you evaluate the general attitudes in society towards women's perception of sexuality after motherhood?	Open-ended

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43	What do you think/feel when you see a woman breastfeeding her baby by exposing her breast in a crowded environment?	Open-ended
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